

isoQUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART IV

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Treatment of α -methyl- α -acetamido- β -phenylpropionic acid with a mixture of polyphosphoric acid and phosphorus oxychloride leads to the formation of 1:3-dimethylisoquinoline, the process involving cyclodehydration, probably followed by decarboxylation and then dehydrogenation.

Snyder and Werber (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2962) made an interesting observation that when *N*-acetylphenylalanine was subjected to the Bischler-Napieralski reaction with a mixture of polyphosphoric acid and phosphorus oxychloride, 1-methylisoquinoline was formed, the process involving cyclodehydration, decarboxylation and dehydrogenation. The exact sequence of the three processes involved has not been established. An observation of a similar nature has also been made from this laboratory (Ghosh and Dutta, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 17, 755) in that, when (α -acetamido- β -phenyl)-ethylmethyl ketone or β -phenyl-substituted analogues are treated with either phosphorus oxychloride or concentrated sulphuric acid, 1-methylisoquinoline derivatives are formed, the process involving cyclodehydration, deacetylation and dehydrogenation.

It has been considered desirable at this stage to investigate the mechanism of the above reaction. That cyclodehydration may be the first step is suggested by the observation of Brodrick and Short (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2587) who have found that certain 3:4-dihydroisoquinolines lose hydrogen atoms when distilled at atmospheric pressure to furnish fully aromatised compounds. Clemo and Hoggarth (*ibid.*, 1954, 95) have observed that 1:2:3:4-tetrahydroisoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid on boiling in ethanol containing sulphuric acid, dehydrogenates to give rise to 3:4-dihydroisoquinoline 3-carboxylic ester. Reference is also made to the observation of Harwood and Johnson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 468) that 6:7-dimethoxy-1-phenyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid, when treated with thionyl chloride, is transformed into the corresponding fully aromatised acid chloride with the loss of two hydrogen atoms. However, some experiments, which have been designed to investigate the sequence of the three processes involved during the Bischler-Napieralski reaction of substituted *N*-acetyl- or *N*-benzoylphenylalanine, are now described in this paper.

It has now been found that when α -methyl- α -acetamido- β -phenylpropionic acid (I: $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$) or its ester (Ghosh, Bhattacharya and Datta, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 417) is treated with a mixture of polyphosphoric acid and phosphorus oxychloride, a base is obtained as a picrate which has been identified as the picrate of 1:3-dimethylisoquinoline (II: $R_2 = Me$) (Witkop, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1424). Similarly, the α -benzamide analogue, under identical condition, has been found to yield a base, identified as 1-phenyl-3-methylisoquinoline (II: $R_2 = Ph$) (Whaley and Hartung, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, 14, 650). These observations obviously show that in

the above reactions decarboxylation has taken place prior to dehydrogenation, as otherwise there is no hydrogen atom at the α -position to the carboxy group in (I) which could be removed. The next point which remains to be settled is whether cyclodehydration has taken place prior to decarboxylation and dehydrogenation or not. With this object in view, 1:3-dimethyl-3-carbomethoxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (III: $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{Me}$) and also the corresponding 3-carboxy compound have been treated with a mixture of polyphosphoric acid and phosphorus oxychloride under conditions as employed in the case of (I: $R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{Me}$), and in each case 1:3-dimethylisoquinoline (II: $R_2 = \text{Me}$) has been obtained and identified as picrate. This conversion has also been effected by heating (III: $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{Me}$) with concentrated alkali (25%) for a prolonged period. All the above observations, when considered, tend to show that in the Bischler-Napieralski reaction of α -methyl- α -acetamido- β -phenylpropionic acid or its ester to furnish 1:3-dimethylisoquinoline, cyclodehydration is probably the first step that is involved, followed by decarboxylation and then dehydrogenation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cyclisation of α -Methyl- α -acetamido- β -phenylpropionic Acid (I: $R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{Me}$): Formation of 1:3-Dimethylisoquinoline.—In a flask, protected from moisture, P_2O_5 (150 g.) was treated with orthophosphoric acid (85%, 98 c.c.) and the mixture heated on a steam-bath for 2 hours with occasional shaking. To the cooled syrupy mass the compound (I: $R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{Me}$; 15.8 g.) and POCl_3 (30.4 c.c.) were added and the mixture, after thorough shaking, was heated at 125° for 8 hours. After cooling, the mixture was treated with ice-water (charcoal) and filtered. The filtrate was basified with NaOH solution under cooling and the liberated red oil was extracted with ether. After removal of the ether, the oil (3 g.) was purified by HCl-NaOH treatment and it furnished in benzene solution a picrate which crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. $181-82^\circ$, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample of the picrate of 1:3-dimethylisoquinoline (Witkop, *loc. cit.*). (Found: C, 52.64; H, 3.92; N, 14.59. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$: C, 52.85; H, 3.62; N, 14.51%.)

The same base, characterised as picrate, was obtained when the ester (I: $R_1 = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{Me}$) was similarly treated with a mixture of polyphosphoric acid and POCl_3 .

Cyclisation of α -Methyl- α -benzamido- β -phenylpropionic Acid (I: $R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{Ph}$): Formation of 1-Phenyl-3-methylisoquinoline.—The benzamido compound was prepared according to the method of Ghosh, Bhattacharya and Datta (*loc. cit.*) and the method of procedure for cyclisation was the same as described above. The isolated base was a

heavy oil which gradually solidified. It was triturated with ligroin (b.p. 60-80°) and crystallised from EtOH in colorless, shining plates, m.p. 90-91°. (Found: C, 87.28; H, 5.92; N, 6.54. $C_{14}H_{13}N$ requires C, 87.67; H, 5.93; N, 6.39%). Whaley and Hartung (*loc. cit.*), who did not describe the method of crystallisation of the above base, recorded m.p. 123-25°.

1:3-Dimethyl-3-carbomethoxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (III: $R_1 = Et$; $R_2 = Me$) was prepared in an analogous manner as the corresponding 3-carbomethoxy compound, described previously (Ghosh, Bhattacharya and Datta, *loc. cit.*), but the yield was improved by the following modification: A mixture of ethyl α -acetamido- α -methyl- β -phenylpropionate (34.2 g.), benzene (342 c.c.) and $POCl_3$ (34.2 c.c.) was heated under reflux on a steam-bath for 4 hours. After distilling off benzene and excess of $POCl_3$, the residue was treated with a cold aqueous NaOH solution (5%), and extracted with ether. The ether extract was shaken with HCl (dilute) and the acid extract, on basification with cold dilute NaOH solution, furnished a dark, heavy oil, distilling at 132-34°/2-3 mm to a colorless oil (14.4 g.). (Found: N, 6.08. $C_{14}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 6.06%).

The above ester was hydrolysed by heating with a dilute NaOH solution (10%) on a steam-bath for about 30 minutes, when a clear solution was obtained. On acidification with HCl (dilute) and scratching, the hydrochloride of 1:3-dimethyl-3-carboxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline was obtained as a crystalline solid, which was recrystallised from ethanol (95%) in colorless, rectangular plates, m.p. 179-80° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.92; Cl, 14.34. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N \cdot HCl$ requires N, 5.84; Cl, 14.82%). The characteristics of this acid have been erroneously recorded in Part III (Ghosh, Bhattacharya and Datta, *loc. cit.*).

Action of a Mixture of Polyphosphoric Acid and $POCl_3$ on (III: $R_1 = Et$; $R_2 = Me$): Formation of 1:3-Dimethylisoquinoline.—The method of procedure was the same as described previously. The reaction mixture was cooled, treated with ice-water and filtered from slight impurity. The filtrate was basified with NaOH and the liberated base (a red oil) was extracted with ether and purified by acid-alkali treatment. The picrate, obtained in benzene solution, was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 181-82°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample of the picrate of 1:3-dimethylisoquinoline (Witkop, *loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 14.48. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{11}N \cdot C_6H_5O_7N_3$: N, 14.51%). 1:3-Dimethylisoquinoline was also isolated on subjecting 1:3-dimethyl-3-carboxy-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline hydrochloride to the reaction of a mixture of polyphosphoric acid and $POCl_3$ under identical conditions.

When a mixture of (III: $R_1 = Et$; $R_2 = Me$) and an aqueous NaOH solution (25%) was heated under reflux on the steam-bath for 16 hours and the mixture cooled and extracted with ether, the ethereal extract yielded a base, the picrate of which was identified to be the picrate of 1:3-dimethylisoquinoline.

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